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INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

GREEN ECONOMY AND ADAPTATION OF INDUSTRY TO CLIMATE CHANGES

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

МЕЂУНАРОДНА НАУЧНА КОНФЕРЕНЦИЈА

ЗЕЛЕНА ЕКОНОМИЈА И АДАПТАЦИЈА ПРИВРЕДЕ НА КЛИМАТСКЕ ПРОМЕНЕ

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FOREWORD

This year, like in the previous 30, we are celebrating Earth Day as part of an international scientific meeting dedicated to the current topic of the day: *Green economy and adaptation of the economy to climate change*. The conference is planned in a hybrid mode (direct and on-line presentations) using the Google meet platform. In 2024, the Conference is organized in cooperation with the Scientific and Professional Society "ECOLOGICA" with the Chamber of Engineers, the Union of Engineers and Technicians, ALFA BK University and the Faculty of Engineering Management, under the auspices of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia.

This year's scientific conference Green economy and adaptation of the economy to climate change is focused on many topics related to the role of remediation of land and water resources in order to adapt to climate change and transform the green economy. The presentations are divided into four scientific sections:

- Remediation of land and water resources in order to create reserves for natural disasters.
- Technogenesis as a cause of climate change.
- Green economic transformation and adaptation to climate change.
- Socio-economic and legal aspects of adaptation to climate change.

The green economy includes many sectors of the economy and industry - recycling municipal waste, permanent disposal of toxic hazardous waste, purification of industrial and municipal water. For the development of the Green Economy, innovative multidisciplinary technologies, resource-saving technologies and the support of financial institutions are necessary in order to solve the problem of environmental protection.

The diversity and multifacetedness of environmental problems associated with numerous natural disasters in the world require a multidisciplinary approach. Research on man-made changes in the environment is necessary, as well as monitoring and assessment of the impact of man-made pollutants on human health.

About 70 scientific presentations by participants from the country and abroad, from various scientific fields, were prepared for presentation at the Conference: adaptation to climate change, green economy, technogenic changes in natural resources, remediation of land and water resources, biotechnological methods of remediation, waste recycling. These works present qualitative analyzes of the impact of the Green Economy on the state of the environment and on the sustainability of various spheres of industry. Special attention is paid to the planning of future international scientific research and the exchange of information in the field of adaptation to climate change and the sustainability of engineering facilities and architectural structures. About 40 foreign scientists from 10 countries sent their papers. The participation of foreign scientists at the International Scientific Conference serves the exchange of information and the development of important directions in the field of transformation of the green economy and adaptation of the economy to climate change. In this way, the cooperation of Russian, Romanian, Belarusian, Moldovan, Chinese, Australian, Turkish, Armenian, Montenegrin and Serbian scientists in new international projects is improved.

Selected works of Serbian and foreign scientists will be included in the International Thematic Collection.

Emeritus prof. dr Larisa Jovanović

BIOLOGICAL PRODUCTIVITY OF FOREST-STEPPE ECOSYSTEMS OF THE RUSSIAN PLAIN IN A CHANGING CLIMATE

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Over the last three decades, the forest-steppe zone of the Russian Plain has warmed significantly, with the average annual air temperature increasing by 2.5°C. The distribution of precipitation over the seasons has become more uneven. The increase in air temperature in summer against the decreasing precipitation leads to increased aridity in the summer period. The local climatic changes in the study area align with the observed trends of climate change in the southern part of European Russia. These trends have a significant impact on the ecosystem resilience and their carbon balance.

The productivity dynamics of old-growth Scots pine stands were largely influenced by both climatic and anthropogenic factors. Current annual phytomass increment in pine stands increased from 1.4 to 2.8 MgC · ha⁻¹ with decreasing anthropogenic impact on the ecosystem. A single 160-year-old pine tree exposed to low levels of anthropogenic impact was found to accumulate 15.2 gC · yr⁻¹ in stem wood over the last 10 years, with variation from 10.31 to 22.55 gC · yr⁻¹ in different years. Conversely, trees exposed to high anthropogenic stress accumulated on average 2.6 gC · yr⁻¹ with a variation from 0.92 to 6.56 gC · yr⁻¹. It was found that Scots pine annual increment was mainly influenced by total atmospheric precipitation. However, the cumulative limiting influence of these factors was always greater than that of each individual factor, showing an even closer relationship with the hydrothermal coefficient. Generally, coniferous forest ecosystem produced 2.36 MgC per unit area each year.

The above-ground NPP of the oak forest ecosystem was lower than that of the pine stands, reaching 2.05 MgC · ha⁻¹ · yr⁻¹. The main productive potential in oak stands was provided by linden and maple. Their NPP was estimated at 0.95 and 0.71 MgC · ha⁻¹ · yr⁻¹, respectively. The coppice oak origin, its depressed state and lower proportion in the stand composition resulted in a significantly lower production – 0.39 MgC · ha⁻¹ · yr⁻¹. On the other hand, in the old-growth forest shelterbelt, where oak originated from seed, productivity was twice higher (0.78 MgC · ha⁻¹ · yr⁻¹). At the same time, the main contribution to the stand's aboveground carbon production was still provided by maple – 1.60 MgC · ha⁻¹ · yr⁻¹. Generally, the total NPP of aboveground phytomass of the forest shelterbelt was 2.83 MgC · ha⁻¹ · yr⁻¹.

The results can be used as a basis for the development of natural resource management strategies that enhance carbon uptake and storage in both natural and anthropogenic forest-steppe ecosystems, as well as for the development of sustainable forestry and agriculture practices, and for the development of technologies that aim to adapt ecosystems to climate change.

Keywords: climate change, carbon balance, NPP, coniferous forest ecosystem, oak forest ecosystem, forest-steppe zone

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